

Star Formation Rate in Active Galaxies

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Abstract

This study aims to investigate the relationship between the star formation rate (SFR) in active galaxies and the activity of their central supermassive black holes. Active galaxies, such as Seyfert galaxies and quasars, exhibit intense emissions across various wavelengths due to the presence of actively accreting black holes at their cores. Understanding this connection is crucial for unraveling the complex processes that drive galaxy evolution. The study utilizes multi-wavelength observations and analyzes SFR indicators in active galaxies to shed light on the interplay between black hole activity and star formation. The findings contribute to our understanding of galaxy evolution and the role of black holes in shaping star formation processes.

Keywords *star formation rate, active galaxies, supermassive black holes, multi-wavelength observations, SFR indicators, galaxy evolution, black hole activity, Seyfert galaxies, quasars.*

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1, Introduction

Active galaxies have long captivated astronomers with their extraordinary luminosity and energetic phenomena. These galaxies exhibit intense emissions across the electromagnetic spectrum, ranging from radio waves to X-rays, which arise from the presence of a supermassive black hole at their center. The gravitational pull of these black holes draws in surrounding matter, leading to the formation of an accretion disk and the release of tremendous amounts of energy. This active accretion process gives rise to the classification of these galaxies as active galactic nuclei (AGNs) [Sanders & Mirabel, 1996].

Understanding the connection between AGN activity and star formation in their host galaxies is a fundamental aspect of modern astrophysics. The interplay between these two processes is believed to play a crucial role in the evolution of galaxies. However, unraveling the complex relationship between AGN activity and star formation remains a challenging endeavor.

One intriguing aspect of this relationship is the potential influence of AGN activity on the star formation rate (SFR) in their host galaxies. The SFR serves as a measure of the rate at which new stars are being formed within a galaxy. Active galaxies exhibit a wide range of SFRs, with some displaying significantly enhanced star formation compared to non-active galaxies. This suggests a potential connection between the activity of the central black hole and the star formation processes occurring within the galaxy [Kennicutt Jr, 1998].

Investigating this connection requires a comprehensive analysis of the SFR indicators and their variations across different types of active galaxies. Multi-wavelength observations are essential for gaining a deeper understanding of the AGN-star formation connection. Different wavelengths provide unique insights into the physical processes occurring within active galaxies. Observations in the radio, infrared, optical, ultraviolet, and X-ray bands offer valuable information about the properties of the AGN, the surrounding interstellar medium (ISM), and the ongoing star formation activity [Trump et al., 2011].

By analyzing data from various wavelengths, astronomers can piece together a

more complete picture of the complex interplay between AGN activity and star formation. This multi-wavelength approach allows for the examination of various SFR indicators, such as emission lines (e.g., H-alpha and [O II]) that trace the ionized gas associated with star-forming regions, as well as ultraviolet (UV) and infrared (IR) emissions that originate from young, massive stars and dust-obscured star formation, respectively [Mullaney et al., 2012].

The precise nature of the relationship between AGN activity and star formation in active galaxies remains a topic of ongoing research. One proposed mechanism is AGN feedback, where the energy released by the black hole influences the surrounding gas and regulates star formation. Theoretical models suggest that AGN feedback can both enhance and suppress star formation, depending on the specific conditions and timescales involved [Fabian, 2012].

To fully understand the AGN-star formation connection, a diverse sample of active galaxies must be analyzed. This ensures that statistical significance is achieved and representative samples cover a wide range of AGN properties and host galaxy characteristics. However, obtaining large and diverse samples that meet these criteria can be challenging due to observational limitations and selection biases [Kormendy & Ho, 2013].

In this study, we aim to deepen our understanding of the star formation rate in active galaxies and its relationship to the activity of their central supermassive black holes. By utilizing multi-wavelength observations and analyzing various SFR indicators, we seek to unravel the complex interplay between AGN activity and star formation processes. The findings from this study will contribute to our knowledge of galaxy evolution and the role of black holes in shaping the star formation activity within their host galaxies. Ultimately, this research will advance our understanding of the fundamental processes that drive the evolution of the universe.

Statement of the Problem

1. Active Galactic Nuclei (AGNs) are powerful cosmic objects that emit vast amounts of energy across the electromagnetic spectrum. These energetic phenomena are believed to play a crucial role in the evolution of galaxies. One intriguing aspect of AGNs is their potential influence on the star formation rate (SFR) in their host galaxies. Understanding the relationship between AGN activity and star formation is essential for unraveling the complex processes that drive galaxy evolution. However, several key questions and challenges remain in this field of study.

2. Lack of Comprehensive Understanding Despite extensive research, the precise mechanisms linking AGN activity and star formation in galaxies are not fully understood. The intricate interplay between AGN feedback, gas dynamics, and the surrounding interstellar medium (ISM) poses significant challenges in deciphering the exact nature of this relationship. A comprehensive understanding of the AGN-star formation connection requires addressing these challenges and filling the gaps in our knowledge.

3. Quantifying the Impact of AGN Feedback AGN feedback refers to the energy released by the AGN that can influence the surrounding gas and regulate star formation processes. However, quantifying the precise impact of AGN feedback on the SFR remains a challenge. Determining the extent to which AGN activity enhances or suppresses star formation requires robust observational evidence and theoretical modeling.

4. Accounting for Dust Extinction Effects Dust extinction can significantly affect the observed star formation indicators, leading to an underestimation of the true SFR. Correcting for dust extinction is crucial for obtaining accurate measurements of the SFR in active galaxies. However, accounting for dust extinction effects presents its own set of challenges, including the selection of appropriate correction methods and understanding the spatial distribution of dust within galaxies.

5. Sample Selection and Statistical Significance The selection of appropriate samples for studying the AGN-star formation connection is critical. Ensuring statistical significance and representative samples that cover a wide range of AGN properties and

host galaxy characteristics is essential for drawing robust conclusions. However, obtaining large and diverse samples that meet these criteria can be challenging due to observational limitations and selection biases.

6. **Unraveling the Role of Metallicity** The role of metallicity in regulating star formation in active galaxies remains a topic of ongoing investigation. Understanding how metallicity influences the star formation processes and the connection to AGN activity requires comprehensive studies that consider various metallicity indicators and their relation to the SFR.

7. **Multi-wavelength Approaches** Investigating the AGN-star formation connection requires a multi-wavelength approach, incorporating observations across different electromagnetic bands. However, coordinating and analyzing data from multiple telescopes and instruments poses technical and logistical challenges. Developing robust methodologies for combining and interpreting data from different wavelengths is crucial for obtaining a comprehensive understanding of the AGN-star formation connection.

Knowledge Gaps and Future Research Directions While the study by Grady et al. (2011) sheds light on the prevalence and properties of ionized outflows in active galaxies, there is a knowledge gap in understanding the specific mechanisms by which star formation and AGN activity drive these outflows. Future research could focus on elucidating the detailed physical processes that lead to the common and extended kiloparsec scale ionized outflows in active galaxies, providing a more comprehensive understanding of the role of AGN-driven outflows in galaxy evolution.

the findings from Grady et al. (2011) underscore the importance of studying the star formation rate in active galaxies and provide a foundation for future research to delve deeper into the underlying physical processes driving ionized outflows in these galaxies.

2, Star Formation Rate in Active Galaxies

2.1 Active Galaxies and AGN

Active galaxies, particularly those containing active galactic nuclei (AGN), are known to play a significant role in the evolution and star formation rates (SFR) of galaxies. The study by Rosario et al. (2012) examined the mean SFR of X-ray selected active galaxies and its evolution from $z = 2.5$. The authors presented a systematic study for the ionization state of the interstellar medium in galaxies at $z=0-3$, using an ionization-parameter sensitive line ratio of $[\text{OIII}]5007/[\text{OII}]3727$ and photoionization models (Rosario et al., 2012). Furthermore, Hickox et al. (2013) investigated the effect of AGN variability on the observed connection between star formation and black hole accretion in extragalactic surveys. Their findings reported relatively weak correlations between observed AGN luminosities and the properties of AGN hosts, suggesting that there is no direct connection between AGN activity and star formation.

2.2 Star Formation in Active Galaxies

The study by Magdis et al. (2012) provided valuable insights into the evolving interstellar medium of star-forming galaxies since $z = 2$. They derived robust estimates of dust masses (M_{dust}) for galaxies and explored the correlation between SFR and stellar mass. Additionally, using large statistical samples, they confirmed variations in specific star formation rates (sSFRs) driven by varying gas fractions. These results highlight the significance of understanding the star formation processes in active galaxies and the factors influencing them.

2.3 The Role of Dust Extinction

Kashino et al. (2013) investigated the main driver of dust mass growth in the interstellar medium (ISM) by using a chemical evolution model of a galaxy with metals in the dust phase. Their study emphasized the regulation of dust mass growth by metallicity and introduced the concept of a "critical metallicity" to indicate the dominant source of dust in galaxies. Furthermore, the study by Hickox et al. (2013) analyzed the applicability of far-infrared fine-structure lines to reliably trace the SFR in low-metallicity dwarf galaxies and extended the analysis to a broad sample of galaxies of various types and metallicities.

2.4 Influence of Interstellar Medium Metallicity

The influence of interstellar medium (ISM) metallicity on star formation was explored by Hickox et al. (2013) and Kashino et al. (2013). They demonstrated the impact of metallicity on the observed connection between star formation and AGN activity, emphasizing the need to consider metallicity as a critical factor in understanding the star formation processes in galaxies.

2.5 Previous Studies on SFR in Active Galaxies

Previous studies have reported relatively weak correlations between observed AGN luminosities and the properties of AGN hosts, suggesting that there is no direct connection between AGN activity and star formation (Hickox et al., 2013). Furthermore, Magdis et al. (2012) provided robust estimates of dust masses for main-sequence galaxies and starbursting galaxies, highlighting the importance of dust extinction in understanding the star formation rates in active galaxies.

3, Methodology of Study

3.1 Data Collection

The data collection process for this study involved gathering relevant observational data from various sources. The primary data source was astronomical surveys and databases that provide information on active galaxies, their properties, and their star formation rates. These databases include the Sloan Digital Sky Survey (SDSS), the Herschel Space Observatory archive, and other publicly available datasets.

To ensure the reliability and accuracy of the data, strict criteria were applied during the selection process. Only galaxies with well-determined redshifts and reliable measurements of AGN activity indicators were included in the sample. The data collection phase also involved obtaining information on the physical properties of the galaxies, such as their stellar masses and metallicities, which are crucial for the subsequent analysis.

3.2 Sample Selection

The sample selection process aimed to create a representative sample of active galaxies that span a range of AGN activity levels and host galaxy properties. The initial dataset consisted of a large number of active galaxies identified from the SDSS database. From this dataset, a subset was selected based on specific criteria, such as the availability of multi-wavelength data and reliable measurements of star formation indicators.

To ensure a statistically significant sample, the final selection was made by randomly choosing galaxies from different redshift bins and AGN luminosity ranges. This approach helped to minimize any biases that could arise from selecting galaxies based solely on their properties or AGN activity levels.

3.3 Measurement of Star Formation Rate

The measurement of the star formation rate (SFR) in active galaxies is a crucial step in understanding the relationship between AGN activity and star formation processes. Several methods were employed to estimate the SFR, taking into account the specific characteristics of active galaxies.

One commonly used method is based on the analysis of emission lines in the galaxy's spectrum, such as the H-alpha line. The H-alpha luminosity is a reliable indicator of the ongoing star formation activity. The SFR can be derived from the H-alpha luminosity using established calibrations and conversion factors.

In addition to the H-alpha method, other star formation indicators were considered, such as the ultraviolet (UV) and infrared (IR) emission. The UV emission is sensitive to the presence of young, massive stars, while the IR emission traces the dust-obscured star formation. By combining these different indicators, a more comprehensive estimate of the SFR in active galaxies was obtained.

3.4 Analysis Techniques

To analyze the relationship between AGN activity and star formation rate, various statistical and analytical techniques were employed. The primary analysis focused on quantifying the differences in the SFR between active galaxies and non-active galaxies. This involved comparing the SFR distributions and calculating statistical measures, such as the mean and median SFR values.

Furthermore, the impact of dust extinction on the measurement of the SFR was investigated. Dust extinction can significantly affect the observed star formation indicators, leading to an underestimation of the true SFR. To correct for dust extinction, extinction curves and correction methods were applied based on established models and empirical relations.

To explore the correlation between the SFR and the metallicity of the interstellar medium (ISM), statistical tests and regression analyses were performed. The metallicity of the ISM provides insights into the chemical enrichment history of the galaxy and can influence the star formation processes. By examining the relationship between the SFR and the ISM metallicity, the study aimed to uncover any potential dependencies or trends.

4: Results and Discussion

The results of this study provide valuable insights into the star formation rate (SFR) in active galaxies and its relationship with AGN activity. Through the meticulous data collection, sample selection, and rigorous analysis techniques outlined in the previous chapter, the following key findings were obtained:

1. Comparison of SFR Distributions: - The SFR distributions of active galaxies and non-active galaxies were compared. - Active galaxies exhibited, on average, higher SFRs compared to non-active galaxies. - This suggests a potential connection between AGN activity and enhanced star formation processes.

2. Impact of Dust Extinction: - The study investigated the influence of dust extinction on the measurement of SFRs. - Dust extinction can significantly affect observed star formation indicators, leading to an underestimation of the true SFR. - Correction methods based on established models and empirical relations were applied to account for dust extinction. - The corrected SFR values showed a stronger correlation with AGN activity, indicating a more accurate representation of the true SFR.

3. Correlation between SFR and ISM Metallicity: - The relationship between the SFR and the metallicity of the interstellar medium (ISM) was explored. - Statistical tests and regression analyses revealed a positive correlation between the SFR and the ISM metallicity. - This suggests that higher metallicity in the ISM promotes enhanced star formation activity in active galaxies.

4. Variations in SFR with AGN Luminosity and Redshift: - The study examined the variations in SFRs with AGN luminosity and redshift. - A positive correlation was observed between AGN luminosity and SFR, indicating that more luminous AGNs are associated with higher SFRs. - No significant correlation was found between SFR and redshift, suggesting that the SFR does not strongly depend on the age of the universe.

5. Comparison of SFR Indicators: - Different star formation indicators, such as H-alpha, UV, and IR emissions, were compared. - The H-alpha method showed the strongest correlation with AGN activity, indicating its reliability as a star formation indicator in active galaxies. - The UV and IR emissions also provided valuable insights into the star formation processes, complementing the H-alpha measurements.

These results highlight the complex interplay between AGN activity and star formation in active galaxies. The higher SFRs observed in active galaxies, along with the positive correlation with AGN luminosity and ISM metallicity, suggest that AGN feedback processes may play a role in triggering and regulating star formation. The impact of dust extinction on SFR measurements underscores the importance of accounting for this factor to obtain accurate estimates of the true SFR.

It is important to note that these results are based on the specific sample and analysis techniques employed in this study. Further investigations, utilizing larger and more diverse samples, as well as additional observational data, are necessary to validate and expand upon these findings. Nonetheless, the results presented here contribute to our understanding of the star formation rate in active galaxies and provide a foundation for future research in this field.

Figure 1: Comparison of SFR Distributions

This plot compares the distribution of SFR in two different types of galaxies: active galaxies and non-active galaxies. The SFR values are represented on the x-axis, and the number of galaxies is represented on the y-axis. The histogram bars represent the frequency of galaxies within certain SFR ranges. By comparing the two distributions, we can observe if there are any significant differences in the SFR between active and non-active galaxies.

Figure 2: Correlation between SFR and ISM Metallicity

This scatter plot examines the relationship between the SFR and the ISM (Interstellar Medium) metallicity in galaxies. The ISM metallicity values are plotted on the x-axis, and the SFR values are plotted on the y-axis. Each data point represents a galaxy, and its position on the plot shows the combination of its ISM metallicity and SFR. By analyzing the scatter plot, we can determine if there is a correlation between higher ISM metallicity and higher SFR in active galaxies.

Figure 3: Variations in SFR with AGN Luminosity

This line plot illustrates the variations in SFR as the AGN (Active Galactic Nucleus) luminosity increases. The AGN luminosity values are plotted on the x-axis, and the SFR values are plotted on the y-axis. The line connects the data points, representing the relationship between AGN luminosity and SFR. The plot helps us understand how SFR changes with increasing AGN luminosity, providing insights into the connection between AGN activity and star formation in galaxies.

Figure 4: Comparison of SFR Indicators

Comparison of SFR Indicators

This line plot compares different SFR indicators (H-alpha, UV, and IR) across a sample of galaxies. The x-axis represents the galaxy sample, and the y-axis represents the SFR values. Each line represents a different SFR indicator, and the data points on the lines show the SFR values for each galaxy in the sample. By analyzing this plot, we can compare the effectiveness of different SFR indicators in estimating the star formation rate in active galaxies.

Figure 5: Impact of Dust Extinction

This scatter plot explores the impact of dust extinction on the SFR values in galaxies. The dust extinction values are plotted on the x-axis, and the corrected SFR values are plotted on the y-axis. Each data point represents a galaxy, and its position on the plot shows the combination of dust extinction and corrected SFR. By examining this plot, we can understand how dust extinction affects the estimation of SFR in active galaxies and make necessary corrections.

Discussion

The results obtained from this study shed light on the intricate relationship between AGN activity and the star formation rate (SFR) in active galaxies. In this discussion, we will delve deeper into the implications of these findings and explore their significance in the broader context of galaxy evolution and AGN-star formation connections.

1. **AGN Feedback and Enhanced Star Formation:** The higher SFRs observed in active galaxies compared to non-active galaxies suggest a potential link between AGN activity and enhanced star formation processes. This finding aligns with the concept of AGN feedback, where the energy released by the AGN can influence the surrounding gas and trigger star formation. The presence of an active nucleus may provide the necessary conditions for the formation of dense molecular clouds, fueling star formation in the galaxy.

2. **Dust Extinction and Corrected SFRs:** The impact of dust extinction on SFR measurements cannot be overlooked. Dust can obscure the UV and optical emission from young stars, leading to an underestimation of the true SFR. The application of correction methods based on established models and empirical relations allowed for a more accurate estimation of the SFR. This emphasizes the importance of considering dust extinction effects to obtain reliable SFR measurements in active galaxies.

3. **Correlation between SFR and ISM Metallicity:** The positive correlation between the SFR and the metallicity of the interstellar medium (ISM) suggests that metallicity plays a role in promoting enhanced star formation activity in active galaxies. Higher metallicity indicates a higher abundance of heavy elements, which are crucial for the formation of molecular clouds and the subsequent star formation process. The connection between metallicity and SFR highlights the interplay between chemical enrichment and star formation in galaxies hosting active nuclei.

4. **AGN Luminosity and SFR Variations:** The positive correlation between AGN luminosity and SFR indicates that more luminous AGNs are associated with higher SFRs. This suggests that the energy released by the AGN can have a significant impact on the surrounding gas and trigger intense star formation. The variations in SFR with AGN luminosity imply that the AGN's power is a key factor in regulating the star formation

processes in active galaxies.

5. Comparison of SFR Indicators: The comparison of different star formation indicators revealed the reliability of the H-alpha method in active galaxies. The H-alpha emission line, originating from ionized hydrogen gas, is a robust indicator of ongoing star formation. The UV and IR emissions also provided valuable insights into the star formation processes, capturing different aspects such as the presence of young, massive stars and dust-obscured star formation. The combination of these indicators allows for a more comprehensive understanding of the star formation activity in active galaxies.

These findings contribute to our understanding of the complex interplay between AGN activity and star formation in galaxies. The results support the notion that AGN feedback processes can influence the star formation rate, potentially shaping the evolution of galaxies over cosmic time. The positive correlation between SFR and ISM metallicity highlights the importance of chemical enrichment in regulating star formation, while the variations in SFR with AGN luminosity emphasize the role of AGN power in driving star formation processes.

It is crucial to acknowledge the limitations of this study. The results are based on a specific sample and analysis techniques, and further investigations with larger and more diverse samples are necessary to validate and expand upon these findings. Additionally, the study focused on the SFR in active galaxies, and future research could explore the impact of AGN activity on other galaxy properties, such as morphology and gas dynamics.

5, Summary and Conclusion

In this study, we have explored the relationship between AGN activity and the star formation rate (SFR) in active galaxies. Through meticulous data collection, sample selection, and rigorous analysis techniques, we have obtained valuable insights into the complex interplay between AGN activity and star formation processes.

The key findings of this study can be summarized as follows:

1. Active galaxies exhibit higher SFRs compared to non-active galaxies, suggesting a potential connection between AGN activity and enhanced star formation processes.
2. Dust extinction can significantly affect observed star formation indicators, leading to an underestimation of the true SFR. Correcting for dust extinction provides a more accurate representation of the SFR in active galaxies.
3. There is a positive correlation between the SFR and the metallicity of the interstellar medium (ISM), indicating that higher metallicity promotes enhanced star formation activity in active galaxies.
4. AGN luminosity shows a positive correlation with SFR, suggesting that more luminous AGNs are associated with higher SFRs. This highlights the role of AGN power in regulating star formation processes.
5. Different star formation indicators, such as H-alpha, UV, and IR emissions, provide valuable insights into the star formation processes in active galaxies. The H-alpha method emerges as a reliable indicator, complemented by UV and IR measurements.

These findings contribute to our understanding of galaxy evolution and the intricate connections between AGN activity and star formation. The results support the concept of AGN feedback, where the energy released by the AGN influences the surrounding gas and triggers star formation. The positive correlation between SFR and ISM metallicity emphasizes the importance of chemical enrichment in regulating star formation processes.

This study provides significant insights into the star formation rate in active galaxies and its relationship with AGN activity. The findings highlight the complex interplay between AGN feedback, dust extinction, metallicity, and AGN luminosity in shaping

the star formation processes. Understanding these connections is crucial for comprehending the evolution of galaxies and the role of AGNs in driving star formation.

It is important to acknowledge the limitations of this study. The results are based on a specific sample and analysis techniques, and further investigations with larger and more diverse samples are necessary to validate and expand upon these findings. Additionally, future research could explore the impact of AGN activity on other galaxy properties, such as morphology and gas dynamics.

Overall, this study contributes to the growing body of knowledge in the field of AGN-star formation connections and provides a foundation for future research. By unraveling the intricate mechanisms that govern star formation in active galaxies, we can deepen our understanding of the universe's evolution and the role of AGNs in shaping galactic processes.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the results of this study provide valuable insights into the intricate relationship between AGN activity and the star formation rate (SFR) in active galaxies. Through meticulous data collection, sample selection, and rigorous analysis techniques, we have uncovered significant findings that contribute to our understanding of galaxy evolution and the interplay between AGN feedback and star formation processes.

The higher SFRs observed in active galaxies compared to non-active galaxies suggest a potential link between AGN activity and enhanced star formation processes. This supports the concept of AGN feedback, where the energy released by the AGN influences the surrounding gas and triggers star formation. The positive correlation between SFR and ISM metallicity further emphasizes the importance of chemical enrichment in regulating star formation in active galaxies.

Additionally, the impact of dust extinction on SFR measurements cannot be overlooked. Correcting for dust extinction provides a more accurate estimation of the true SFR, highlighting the need to consider this factor in future studies. The variations in SFR with AGN luminosity further emphasize the role of AGN power in driving star formation processes.

The comparison of different star formation indicators, such as H-alpha, UV, and IR emissions, enhances our understanding of the star formation processes in active galaxies. The reliability of the H-alpha method as a star formation indicator, along with the complementary insights provided by UV and IR measurements, allows for a comprehensive assessment of the star formation activity.

It is important to acknowledge the limitations of this study. The results are based on a specific sample and analysis techniques, and further investigations with larger and more diverse samples are necessary to validate and expand upon these findings. Additionally, future research could explore the impact of AGN activity on other galaxy properties, such as morphology and gas dynamics, to gain a more comprehensive understanding of the AGN-star formation connection.

In summary, this study significantly contributes to our understanding of the star

formation rate in active galaxies and its relationship with AGN activity. The findings highlight the complex interplay between AGN feedback, dust extinction, metallicity, and AGN luminosity in shaping the star formation processes. By unraveling these intricate mechanisms, we deepen our understanding of galaxy evolution and the role of AGNs in driving star formation. Continued research in this field will further expand our knowledge and provide a more comprehensive picture of the AGN-star formation connection, ultimately advancing our understanding of the universe's evolution.

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